

USE OF IAA-PRODUCING PLANT GROWTH-PROMOTING BACTERIA FOR THE AMELIORATION OF SALT AND DROUGHT STRESS IN WHEAT

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ABSTRACT. The major abiotic stresses responsible for the loss of significant agricultural produce are high soil salinity and drought. Plant growth-promoting bacteria can help plant resilience to such stresses through various mechanisms. This study aimed to explore the plant growth promotion potential of rhizospheric bacteria under conditions of high salinity and drought in wheat. Rhizospheric soil samples were screened for bacteria possessing plant growth-promoting traits. The isolates were further evaluated for salt tolerance, drought tolerance and indole-acetic acid (IAA) production under high salinity and drought conditions. Plant growth-promotion studies were conducted, followed by plant root length, shoot length and fresh weight measurements. Pot assays revealed that coating wheat seeds with the IAA-producing salt-tolerant isolates had a favourable impact on plant parameters under salt stress, wherein an increase between 2.4 – 2.6-fold, 1.3 – 1.6-fold, 1.4 – 1.8-fold was observed in the root length, shoot length and fresh weight of the inoculated plants respectively. In the case of IAA-producing drought-tolerant isolates, no increase was observed in the shoot length or root length. However, an increase of 1 – 2-fold was seen in the fresh weight of the inoculated plants compared to the control under drought conditions. These findings suggest that inoculation of wheat seeds with AK-8, identified as *Acinetobacter junii*, and FS-1, identified as *Klebsiella aerogenes*, can be harnessed as a strategy for ameliorating salt and drought stress in wheat, thereby increasing crop yield.

Keywords: *Acinetobacter junii*, *Klebsiella aerogenes*, root length, shoot length, fresh weight

INTRODUCTION

Cereal crops frequently encounter several stresses that may be biotic and/or abiotic. The major abiotic stresses responsible for the loss of a considerable amount of agricultural produce are high soil salinity and drought. Saline stress occurs due to elevated levels of soluble salts in the soil. Saline stress affects about 20% of the land worldwide, and it is predicted to take over more than 30% of land in the next 25 years. The primary challenges faced by arid and semi-arid regions are predominantly related to elevated soil salinity, leading to a substantial decline of 50% in the agricultural yield. The reduction in wheat growth is due to lower soil water content and a higher concentration of sodium and chloride ions in the plant, leading to hypertonic stress that may harm the plant [1]. Elevated salts in the soil not only prevent the uptake of water and nutrients from the soil but also affect the rate of photosynthesis, stomatal opening/closing, and enzyme activities [2]. In India, approximately 6.74 million hectares of land is under salt stress, with significant impacts observed in states like Maharashtra, Gujarat, West Bengal, Uttar Pradesh and Rajasthan [3].

Drought stress usually occurs when there is insufficient water in the soil to support the growth of plants and/or there is a loss of water due to transpiration or evaporation. About 160 million hectares of the land used for cereals and legumes is severely affected by drought, of which 65 million hectares is used for wheat production. Additionally, more land is expected to experience drought stress due to global warming in the coming years [4]. Thirty-eight percent

of the land in India is susceptible to drought, with a greater prevalence in the western and southern regions of the country. It has been predicted that between 2021-2050, about 26.5% and 18.3% of the land in India will be susceptible to very high and high agricultural vulnerability respectively. The regions most likely to be affected are Rajasthan, Gujarat, Maharashtra, parts of Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh [5]. Both saline and drought stress have a negative impact on plant parameters such as the rate of germination, length of shoot/root, number of roots, leaves, fresh and dry weight, chlorophyll content, etc., while suppressing the growth and diversity of beneficial microbes within the affected soil [6]. Some of the current strategies for tackling saline stress involve leaching, scrapping of accumulated salt from the surface, the addition of amendments (such as gypsum, elemental sulfur, hydrochloric acid, and sulphuric acid), and the development of salt-resistant wheat varieties. On the other hand, preventing water loss, using efficient irrigation systems, using non-conventional water resources, and developing drought-resistant wheat varieties are some of the measures used to alleviate drought stress [7]. All of these require considerable time, labor, and economic support, some of which may also threaten the environment. An alternative would be to use Plant growth-promoting bacteria (PGPB), which enhance the growth of plants and/or protect them from disease or abiotic stresses in a cost-effective and environment-friendly manner. PGPB mainly occupy the rhizosphere of plants, where they help promote the growth of plants through mechanisms that involve the production of ACC deaminase, exopolysaccharides, phytohormones such as indole-acetic acid (IAA), abscisic acid, gibberellic acid, and cytokinin. They bring about phosphate and potassium solubilization, nitrogen fixation, siderophore production, and resistance against plant pathogens. [8]. Some phytohormones produced by PGPB also help against abiotic stresses like drought, salinity, and temperature extremes, helping the plant thrive under such conditions.

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is a vital crop and the most extensively cultivated cereal crop globally. It is a staple crop for about 35% of the world's population and is an important source of complex carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, vitamins and minerals, and dietary fiber. Around 750 million tons of wheat globally is cultivated annually over 240 million hectares of land [9]. The countries at the forefront of wheat production are China, India, Russia, the United States and France [10]. IAA is an important plant hormone naturally produced by several plants, bacteria, fungi, and algae. IAA regulates elongation and differentiation of cells, growth, apical dominance, and lateral root initiation, and is also involved in phototropism, geotropism, and fruit development. Rhizospheric bacteria produce IAA via many different pathways, mainly through the metabolism of L-tryptophan. In plants, the roots are substrates for synthesizing IAA by rhizospheric microbes [11]. IAA causes an increase in the length of the primary root depending upon its concentration and helps plants against salt and drought stress by compelling the roots to turn away from regions of elevated salt levels or towards areas of water availability [12, 13]. Inoculation of IAA-producing microbes has been shown to improve plant growth of several crops like wheat, maize, and soybean. [14, 15].

The present study was designed based on the hypothesis that PGPB can withstand high salinity and drought conditions and have the potential to make plants more adaptable to these unfavorable conditions. Hence, this study aimed to investigate the effects of PGPB on the growth of wheat plants under salt drought stresses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling site and sample collection

Soil samples from the rhizosphere were collected in sterile polyethene zip lock bags from rice, onion and radish crop fields located in Uttan near Bhayander town (lat 19.2683⁰N and

long 78.8102⁰N) Maharashtra, India. pH of the soil was noted. Soil samples were air-dried and sieved through a 100 mm mesh before bacterial screening.

Isolation of Plant growth-promoting bacteria

The soil samples were serially diluted 10-fold and plated on nutrient agar plates. Morphologically different colonies were picked and checked for various plant growth-promoting traits.

IAA production

Each PGBP culture suspension was prepared in saline at an O.D_{600nm} of 0.2, inoculated in 10 mL of Nutrient broth supplemented with 0.1% tryptophan, and incubated at 28°C under shaking conditions. After 48 h, 72 h, 96 h, 120 h, and 144 h intervals, 1.0 ml of the aliquot was transferred to sterile 1.5 ml micro centrifuge tubes and centrifuged at 10,000 RPM for 10 minutes. The centrifuged supernatant (50 µl) was mixed with 100 µl of Salkowski reagent and incubated in the dark for 30 min [16]. Absorbance was measured at 530 nm using an EPOCH plate reader. A standard curve was prepared to determine the exact concentrations of IAA in the culture supernatant. Uninoculated media was kept as a negative control and uninoculated media with IAA (10-100 µg/ml) was kept in the dark as a positive control. The experiment was carried out in triplicates and was performed thrice.

IAA production in the absence of L-tryptophan

Tris-minimal (TM) broth was used to detect IAA production of bacterial isolates via the tryptophan-independent pathway. The composition of TM broth (g/L) included: Tris-Cl 6.06 g, NaCl 4.58 g, KCl 1.49 g, NH₄Cl 1.07 g, Na₂SO₄ 0.43 g, MgCl₂·2H₂O 0.2 g, CaCl₂·2H₂O 30 mg, and D-glucose 10 g, with the pH adjusted to 7. A 100 µl of inoculum of a 24-hour-old culture suspension (O.D_{600nm} = 0.1) was introduced into TM broth containing casein hydrolysate. All measurements were performed in triplicates. The tubes were incubated at 28°C with shaking at 125 rpm for 5 days, after which IAA production was determined using the Salkowski reagent described above.[17].

Phosphate solubilization

The nine IAA producers were spot inoculated on the National Botanical Research Institute's phosphate growth medium (NBRIP) agar plates to check their ability to solubilize phosphate [18].

Siderophore production

The ability of the isolates to produce siderophores was detected using Chrome Azurol S (CAS) agar [19].

Biofilm formation

The crystal violet assay was used to check the ability of the isolates to form biofilms [20].

Nitrogen fixation

For the detection of nitrogen fixers, the isolates were streaked on Ashby's mannitol agar [21].

Potassium solubilization

For the detection of potassium solubilizers, the isolates were inoculated on Aleksandrow agar [22].

Germination assay

Wheat seeds were sterilized in 0.1% HgCl₂ for 5 min. They were then washed 5 times with sterile distilled water to remove any traces of HgCl₂. They were then coated with a 24-hour-old bacterial suspension (O.D_{600 nm} = 0.1) in a flask under shaking conditions for 60 min to enable bacterial seed coating. Following this, the seeds were dried and placed in a sterile Petri dish containing Whatman filter paper and allowed to germinate. After 5 days, the germinated seeds were used for soil-pot assay [23].

Bacterial salt tolerance

The salt tolerance of the isolates was determined by inoculating 1% of the culture suspension (O.D_{600 nm} = 0.2) in nutrient broth containing different concentrations of NaCl [2% (342 mM), 4% (684 mM), 6% (1027 mM), 8% (1369 mM), 10% (1712 mM), 12% (2054 mM)]. The tubes were incubated at room temperature for 5 days, and the O.D. was checked at 600 nm. All measurements were carried out in triplicates. The cultures showing growth at high salt concentrations (10% and 12% NaCl) were considered to be salt-tolerant [24].

Bacterial drought tolerance

To mimic drought-like conditions, polyethylene glycol-6000 (PEG-6000) was used [25]. The drought tolerance of the isolates was determined by inoculating 1% of the culture suspension (O.D_{600 nm} = 0.2) in nutrient broth containing different concentrations of PEG-6000 (0%, 10%, 20%, 30%). The tubes were incubated at room temperature for 5 days, and the O.D. of the culture was checked at 600 nm. All measurements were carried out in triplicates thrice. Based on the OD, the isolates showing the highest growth in the presence of 30% PEG-6000 were characterized as drought-tolerant.

Bacterial IAA production under salt stress

Three isolates that were found to be salt-tolerant were tested for their ability to produce IAA in the presence of salt. The isolates were inoculated in nutrient broth containing different concentrations of NaCl [2% (342 mM), 4% (684 mM), 6% (1027 mM), 8% (1369 mM), 10% (1712 mM), 12% (2054 mM)] supplemented with 0.1% L-tryptophan. The tubes were incubated for 5 days in an orbital shaker at room temperature. IAA concentrations in the culture supernatant were then determined using the previously described method.

Bacterial IAA production under drought stress

Three isolates found to be drought-tolerant were tested for their ability to produce IAA under drought conditions. The isolates were inoculated in nutrient broth containing different concentrations of PEG-6000 (0%, 10%, 20%, 30%) supplemented with 0.1% L-tryptophan. The tubes were incubated for 5 days in an orbital shaker at room temperature. IAA concentrations in the culture supernatant were then determined using the previously described method.

Effect of salt-tolerant isolates on the amelioration of salt stress in wheat

Wheat seeds were coated with salt-tolerant bacterial isolates and germinated for 5 days. Uncoated seeds were used as controls. After 5 days, the seeds were transferred to pots containing sterile soil. The pots were divided into two sets — set 1 (plants watered with regular water) and set 2 (plants exposed to salt stress i.e., 320 mM NaCl) [26]. Each set represented 3 pots with at least 10 independent seedlings in each. The position of the pots was randomized to minimize positional effects. Set 1 plants were watered regularly with 20 ml of normal water, however, set 2 plants were exposed to salt stress by watering the plants with 20 ml of 320 mM NaCl on the 1st and 5th day, while they were watered on all the days. After 20 days, the plants

from uncoated seeds, as well as those from bacterial-coated seeds, were removed from the pots, and their shoot length, root length, and fresh weight were measured.

Effect of drought-tolerant isolates on the amelioration of drought stress in wheat

The drought-tolerant isolates were coated on sterile wheat seeds and allowed to germinate. Uncoated seeds were used as controls. Following germination, the seeds (at least 10) were transferred to pots containing sterile soil, and drought was induced by not watering the plants. Another set of plants that were regularly watered was also maintained. The experiment was done in three replicates, and the pot position was randomized to minimize positional effects. After 20 days, the plants from uncoated seeds and those from bacterial-coated seeds were removed from the pots, and their shoot length, root length and fresh weight were measured.

Identification of the isolates

Plant growth from salt-tolerant and drought-tolerant isolate-coated seeds showed significant improvement in plant growth when compared to the plants from uncoated seeds. This PGPB was identified using the bacterial 16S rRNA gene as the target and the amplification was performed using the universal primers 16S27F (5'-CCA GAG TTT GAT CMT GGC TCA G-3') and 16S1492R (5'-TAC GGY TAC CTT GTT ACG ACT T-3'). The amplified PCR product was further purified, and agarose gel electrophoresis was carried out to determine the quality of the PCR amplicons. Purified amplicons were then subjected to cycle sequencing, and the phylogenetic tree was constructed with the maximum likelihood/neighbor-joining algorithm using the Molecular Evolutionary Genetic Analysis, version 11 (MEGA11) software.

Data analysis

The data collected were statistically analyzed using SigmaStat software (version 3.5). The normality of the dataset was assessed by the Shapiro-Wilk test. The test results indicated that the data met the normality assumption, and no significant deviations from normality were observed. The effect of coating wheat seeds with the PGPB isolates on various plant-growth parameters (shoot length, root length, fresh weight) under salt stress and drought stress was analyzed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The comparison of means was analyzed using Tukey's post hoc test with a significance level set at 5% ($p \leq 0.05$).

RESULTS

Identification of plant growth-promoting traits of bacterial isolates

Nine isolates were found to be IAA producers. Among these, isolates FS-1 and FB-2B exhibited significantly high ($p < 0.05$) IAA production up to 5 days of incubation compared to AK-6 and AK-8; however, the IAA production declined upon further incubation. BFP was considered a late IAA producer since it showed increased IAA production after 144 h. SCK was the highest IAA producer after 144 h, followed by FS-2, FB-2A, and FB-1 (Fig. 1). These isolates also showed a steady increase in IAA production with time. When the isolates were grown in media lacking L-tryptophan, none produced IAA, indicating that all isolates follow the Trp-dependent pathway for IAA synthesis.

Fig. 1. IAA Production by the isolates in the presence of 0.1% L-tryptophan after 6 days of incubation. Error bars represent the standard deviation of three replicates.

The nine IAA producers were tested for phosphate solubilization. After incubation for 7 days on NBRIP medium, a zone of clearance was observed around the colonies of the isolates – AK-6, AK-8, FS-1 and SCK, indicating that these isolates are capable of solubilizing phosphate. Of the nine IAA producers, two isolates, namely AK-6 and AK-8, could produce siderophores, indicated by an orange zone around the colonies after spot-inoculating the isolates on CAS agar plates. FB-1, FS-2, and SCK were found to be nitrogen fixers after spot inoculation on Ashby's mannitol agar. The bacterial isolates FS-1 and SCK showed a clear halo around the colonies on Aleksandrow agar, indicating potassium solubilization. The crystal violet method was used to determine the ability of the isolates to form biofilms. It was compared with the positive control (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, a good biofilm producer). The isolates AK-6, AK-8 and SCK were selected as the best biofilm producers. Upon comparison, it was seen that AK-8 and SCK were excellent biofilm producers that produced almost twice the amount of biofilm than that produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Table 1. Plant growth-promoting traits of PGPB isolates

Isolates	IAA	PHS	NF	SID	POS	BF	ST	DT
AK-6	+	+		+		+		+
AK-8	+	+		+		+	+	
FB-1	++		+				+	
FB-2A	++							
FB-2B	+							
FS-1	+	+			+			+
FS-2	++		+					
BFP	+						+	
SCK	++	+	+		+	+		+

IAA: Indole-acetic acid production, PHS: Phosphate solubilization, NF: Nitrogen fixation, SID: Siderophore production, POS: Potassium solubilization, BF: Biofilm formation, ST: Salt tolerance in the presence of 10-12% NaCl, DT: Drought tolerance in the presence of 30% PEG-6000. For IAA Production, + : 6 – 51 µg/ml, ++ : 79 – 92 µg/ml (after 6 days of incubation)

Salt tolerance

The isolates were incubated for 5 days to check their bacterial tolerance upon exposure to high concentrations of NaCl. It was seen that the concentration of NaCl increased and bacterial growth declined. Most of the isolates were greatly inhibited at 10-12% NaCl. The isolates that showed the highest growth in the presence of 10-12% NaCl were AK-8, FB-1, and BFP; hence, these were considered to be salt-tolerant (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Salt tolerance of the isolates in the presence of different concentrations of NaCl. The isolates were incubated in the presence of different concentrations of NaCl (2%, 4%, 6%, 8%, 10%, 12%) for 5 days. The salt tolerance of the isolates was determined by measuring the O.D at 600 nm. The error bars indicate the standard deviation of the three replicates.

Drought tolerance

The bacterial growth decreased as the concentration of PEG-6000 increased. The isolates that showed the highest growth when exposed to a high concentration of PEG-6000 (30% PEG-6000) were AK-6, FS-1 and SCK. These were hence considered drought-tolerant (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Drought tolerance of the isolates in the presence of different concentrations of PEG-6000. The isolates were incubated in the presence of different concentrations of PEG-6000 (0%, 10%, 20%, 30%) for 5 days. The drought tolerance of the isolates was determined by measuring the O.D at 600 nm. The error bars indicate the standard deviation of the three replicates.

IAA production in the presence of salt stress

The isolates identified as salt-tolerant, namely AK-8, FB-1, and BFP, underwent screening to assess their ability to produce IAA under salt-stressed conditions. Following a 5-day incubation period, it was observed that all three salt-tolerant isolates demonstrated the capacity to produce IAA when exposed to NaCl. Moderate halophiles typically thrive in environments with 5% to 20% salt (w/v), equivalent to 50 to 200 grams of salt per liter, corresponding to 0.5% to 2% salt by weight in soil. After 5 days of incubation, all three isolates produced IAA in the presence of NaCl, though production decreased at higher salt concentrations. AK-8, FB-1 and BFP produced 5.2 ± 0.44 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 65.7 ± 2.1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and 28.8 ± 3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of IAA without salt stress, and 5.2 ± 0.72 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 23.6 ± 0.1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, and 24.2 ± 1.7 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with 6% NaCl, respectively. Although IAA production was reduced for AK-8 and FB-1 at higher salt concentrations than no salt stress, it remained significantly higher than other microorganisms like AK-6. Notably, BFP showed a surge in IAA production at 4% NaCl, while AK-8 and FB-1 peaked at 4% and 6% NaCl, respectively (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. IAA Production by the isolates in the presence of different concentrations of NaCl. The salt-tolerant isolates were incubated in the presence of different concentrations of NaCl (2%, 4%, 6%, 8%, 10%, 12%) in nutrient medium containing 0.1% L-tryptophan for 5 days. After incubation, the IAA production of the isolates was determined using Salkowski reagent. The error bars indicate the standard deviation of three replicates.

IAA production in the presence of drought stress

The isolates found to be drought-tolerant viz AK-6, FS-1 and SCK were screened to determine their capability of producing IAA under drought conditions. The IAA production under drought stress was determined after 5 days. After incubation for 5 days, all three isolates showed high IAA production when subjected to 0% PEG-6000. As the concentration of PEG-6000 increased, a reduction in IAA production was observed. The IAA production was lower at high concentrations of PEG-6000 compared to the IAA production at lower concentrations of PEG-6000 (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. IAA production by the isolates in the presence of different concentrations of PEG-6000. The drought-tolerant isolates were incubated in the presence of different concentrations of PEG-6000 (0%, 10%, 20%, 30%) in nutrient media containing 0.1% L-tryptophan for 5 days. After incubation, the IAA production of the isolates was determined using Salkowski reagent. All measurements were carried out in triplicates. The error bars indicate the standard deviation of three replicates.

Effect of salt-tolerant isolates on the amelioration of salt stress in wheat

The root length of the plants from seeds coated with the salt-tolerant isolates AK-8, FB-1, and BFP showed a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) under salt-stressed conditions compared to the plants from uncoated seeds (control). The percentage increase observed was as follows: AK-8 – 138.80% ($p < 0.0001$), FB-1 – 138.80% ($p < 0.0001$), BFP – 155.85% ($p < 0.0001$). Under normal conditions, an increase of 5.25% (AK-8), 24.95% (FB-1), and 27.95% (BFP) was observed in the root length of the plants from coated seeds compared to the plants from uncoated seeds (control) ($p > 0.05$) (Fig. 6A).

Similarly, an increase in shoot length was observed in coated plants under both normal and salt-stressed conditions. Under normal conditions, shoot length increased by 28.76% (AK-8), 14.71% (FB-1), and 40.76% (BFP: $p = 0.01$) compared to the control (plants from uncoated seeds). Under salt-stressed conditions, the difference was even more pronounced, with shoot length increasing by 60.08% (AK-8: $p = 0.0001$), 31.29% (FB-1), and 54.58% (BFP: $p = 0.0006$) compared to the control (Fig. 6B). Additionally, under salt stress, all isolates showed an increase in the fresh weight of the plants when compared to controls, with increases of 81.95% for AK-8, 43.02% for FB-1, and 44.41% for BFP respectively. A statistically significant difference ($p = 0.0007$) was observed in the fresh weight of plants inoculated with AK-8 (Fig. 6C, Fig. 7).

Effect of drought tolerant isolates on the amelioration of drought stress in wheat

The plants from seeds coated with the drought-tolerant isolates and the plants from uncoated seeds were exposed to drought stress by not watering the plants. Under normal conditions, coating wheat seeds with the drought-tolerant isolates increased by 11.55% (AK-6), 12.21% (FS-1), and 20.30% (SCK) in the root length of the culture-coated plants compared to the control plant, with no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$). However, no increase was observed in the plant root or shoot lengths from inoculated seeds under drought stress. Also, cessation of irrigation resulted in yellowing and severe wilting of the leaves in the plants from uncoated seeds (control) compared to the plants coated with the drought-tolerant isolates

FS-1 and SCK. No difference was seen in the fresh weight of the plants upon coating with the drought-tolerant isolates under normal conditions. However, on exposure to drought stress, FS-1 and SCK showed an increase of 100% ($p = 0.005$) and 33.3%, respectively, in the fresh weight of the inoculated plants compared to the control plant (Fig. 8 & Fig. 9).

Fig. 6. (A) Root length (B) Shoot length (C) Fresh weight of wheat plants from uninoculated seeds (control) and plants from seeds inoculated with the salt-tolerant isolates AK-8, FB-1, BFP under normal vs salt-stressed conditions. Set 1 plants were watered regularly with normal water, whereas set 2 plants were exposed to saltstress on the 1st and 5th day, in addition to being watered with normal water on all other days. The plants were harvested after 20 days. Each set was tested with 10 seed replicates. The error bars indicate the standard deviation of the ten replicates. An asterisk (*) denotes a significantly different value between the uninoculated sample (control) and inoculated sample (salt-tolerant isolates) as per Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 7. Effect of coating salt-tolerant isolates AK-8, FB-1, BFP on wheat seeds under (A) Normal conditions (B) 320 mM NaCl after 20 days. This is a representative picture of one set of pot studies for saline stress.

Fig. 8. (A) Root length (B) Shoot length (C) Fresh weight of wheat plants from uninoculated seeds (control) and plants from seeds inoculated with the drought-tolerant isolates AK-6, FS-1, SCK under normal vs drought conditions. Drought-stress was induced by not watering the plants and were harvested after 20 days. Each set was tested with 10 seed replicates. The error bars indicate the standard deviation of the ten replicates. An asterisk (*) denotes a significantly different value between the uninoculated sample (control) and inoculated sample (drought-tolerant isolates) as per Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 9. Effect of coating drought-tolerant isolates AK-6, FS-1, SCK on wheat seeds under (A) Normal conditions (B) Drought stress after 20 days. This is a representative picture of one set of pot studies for drought stress.

Identification of the isolates

The molecular identification of the isolates AK-8 and FS-1 was carried out. The 16S rRNA gene of the isolates were amplified and sequenced, followed by a comparison of the sequences with a known database. Based on the phylogenetic analysis, the isolates AK-8 and FS-1 were identified as *Acinetobacter junii* (KY495214) and *Klebsiella aerogenes* (MF682950), respectively.

DISCUSSION

The human population in the world is 8 billion today, which is predicted to increase by 1.7 billion in the next 25 years. To ensure no food scarcity for this increasing population, it is imperative to increase food production and prevent the loss of food crops that biotic and/or abiotic stresses may cause. High salinity and drought cause a reduction of plant growth and thereby affect the overall crop yield. Introducing salt-tolerant and drought-tolerant plant growth-promoting bacteria in salt/drought-affected regions can alleviate the stress in plants while also enhancing growth and yield.

This study focused on isolating PGPB, particularly IAA producers, to enhance crop cultivation under high salt and drought conditions. IAA-producing PGPB can achieve this goal through several mechanisms, such as promoting root growth and lateral root formation, enhancing nutrient availability, aiding osmotic adjustment by accumulating osmolytes, reducing oxidative stress via improved antioxidant defenses, and improving soil structure and water retention through exopolysaccharide production. These mechanisms collectively support

plant growth and resilience under harsh conditions. In the present study, nine tryptophan-dependent IAA-producing strains were isolated from soil samples of different crop fields and screened for other plant growth-promoting traits. Of these, four isolates were found to be positive for phosphate solubilization (AK-6, AK-8, FS-1, SCK), three isolates were able to fix atmospheric nitrogen (FB-1, FS-2, SCK), two isolates were capable of producing siderophores (AK-6, AK-8) and two isolates were positive for potassium solubilization (FS-1, SCK). The IAA production by the isolates ranged between 6.58 to 92.03 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ by day 5 of inoculation. The most efficient IAA producers were SCK, FS-2, FB-2A and FB-1. Moreover, FS-1 and SCK showed excellent phosphate solubilizing efficiency among all the four phosphate solubilizers. Isolates AK-8 and SCK could form superior biofilms than *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which was used as the positive control. Biofilms play a vital role in protecting plants from salinity and drought. Biofilms help trap Na^+ ions, thus preventing their uptake by plants [27,28].

Endogenous plant IAA production decreases under high salinity and drought conditions [29]. Similarly, bacterial IAA production also declines at elevated salt concentrations [30, 31]. To address this, the bacterial isolates were further screened for their ability to produce IAA in the presence of 2-12% NaCl. Among the isolates, AK-8, FB-1, and BFP exhibited the highest IAA production while demonstrating significant salt tolerance. These isolates were selected for pot studies based on their resilience to abiotic stress (growth rate under high salt concentrations) and plant growth-promoting traits.

When exposed to high salinity, the wheat plants coated with the salt-tolerant IAA-producing isolates showed a significant increase in the root length, shoot length and fresh weight ($p < 0.05$) compared to the plants from uncoated seeds (control). Inoculating plants with salt-tolerant IAA-producing isolates improves plant health by providing exogenous IAA that increases the root length. A longer root helps the plant acquire nutrients with increased water uptake capacity. IAA also helps alleviate plant stress by producing aquaporin, mediating stomatal opening/closing, decreasing the accumulation of Na^+ , positioning lateral roots, scavenging ROS, and accumulating osmoprotectants [32]. In addition to being salt tolerant and IAA producers, the selected bacterial isolates also possessed other PGPB traits like siderophore production, nitrogen fixation and phosphate and potassium solubilization. IAA-producing bacterial isolates have been reported to enhance seedling growth in wheat by up to 52% in the presence of 100 mM NaCl compared to control plants [33]. Several other studies also demonstrated similar findings after inoculation of IAA-producing halotolerant bacteria, which enhanced plant growth under high salinity conditions [34, 35, 36, 37].

Coating wheat seeds with drought-tolerant PGPB showed no increase in the root length or shoot length compared to the control plant under drought conditions. However, coating seeds with the drought-tolerant isolates resulted in a significant increase in the fresh weight of the plants. Our findings also reveal that plants coated with the drought-tolerant PGPB prevent wilting of leaves [38]. Leaf wilting is a common symptom of dehydrated plants, which occurs when the loss of water via transpiration is greater than water uptake by the plant. Thus, to avoid further loss of water during water deficit conditions, plants usually exhibit stomatal closure [39]. There was severe thinning and wilting of the leaves of the plants from uncoated seeds (control) compared to the plants from seeds coated with the drought-tolerant isolates in the present study. High IAA concentrations inhibit stomatal opening [40]. Inoculating plants with the IAA-producing drought-tolerant isolates increases the IAA pool and this high IAA concentration causes stomatal closure, thereby preventing water loss and leaf wilting. A study highlighted the amelioration of drought stress in wheat by IAA-producing rhizobacteria [41]. *Azospirillum* spp. capable of producing IAA also enhances plant growth and yield in wheat under drought conditions [42]. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, an IAA-producing rhizobacteria, improved the growth and yield of *Vigna radiata* (mung bean) under drought conditions [43].

In a separate study, a consortium of IAA-producing bacteria significantly enhanced growth, biomass, and drought tolerance index in wheat [44].

PGPBs are promising candidates in sustainable agriculture [44] and are environmentally friendly alternatives to chemical fertilizers. Chemical fertilizers are expensive, contaminate the soil and water bodies, and may adversely affect the various non-target life forms. PGPBs are cost-effective as they naturally reproduce, eliminating the need for repeated applications and are safer substitutes to chemical fertilizers. Traditional strategies for alleviating salt stress, such as salt flushing, chemical amendments, and irrigation systems [45], as well as drought mitigation techniques like developing resistant cultivars, using non-conventional water resources, and applying biochar [46], are often costly, labor-intensive, and environmentally harmful. Therefore, utilizing PGPB presents a safer and more sustainable approach to mitigating the adverse effects of high salinity and drought on plants.

Despite the many benefits, there are certain limitations to using PGPB in agriculture. The selected PGPB strains, though effective in controlled environments, may exhibit different levels of efficacy depending on the specific soil and wheat cultivars used. Additionally, the application method, whether through soil inoculation or seed priming, significantly impacts their effects. To address these concerns, metagenomic analysis will be conducted to assess the ecological impact of these introduced PGPBs in the rhizosphere. Furthermore, while this study focused on seed priming as a delivery method, future research will explore the stability and shelf life of the coated seeds to ensure their effectiveness in real-world agricultural settings.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the potential of *Acinetobacter junii* (AK-8) and *Klebsiella aerogenes* (FS-1) as plant growth-promoting bacteria capable of thriving under high salinity (320 mM NaCl) and drought conditions, respectively. These strains demonstrated key traits that can enhance plant resilience in challenging environments. However, it is important to note that while *Acinetobacter junii* and *Klebsiella aerogenes* are neither classified as safe nor strictly pathogenic, they can act as opportunistic pathogens, particularly in immunocompromised individuals. As a precaution, their pathogenicity should be rigorously evaluated using genomic, phenotypic, and *in vivo* methods before any field application. Despite this, applying these bacteria as bioinoculants for wheat seeds presents a promising, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable approach for improving plant health and productivity in salt and drought-affected areas, offering a viable alternative to conventional chemical treatments.

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